

Studies on the Stereoregularity of Poly(methyl methacrylate)

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In Ziegler-Natta catalyst systems, the nature of the catalysts has a profound influence upon the stereoregularity of polymer chain. Currently, free radical and anionic mechanisms with Ziegler catalysts are distinguished via nmr analysis of the polymer structure¹. Successful use of ¹H nmr analysis in establishing the mechanisms of polymerization with such Ziegler-Natta catalyst systems

have already been reported^{3,5}. Such studies on the mechanistic aspects of polymerizations with zinc alkyls are essentially unknown. However, Soga and Keii⁴ examined the kinetics of polymerization of propylene with TiCl_3 - ZnEt_2 and AlEt_3 . The main conclusion from this kinetic study was that the structures of the polymerization centers were different. Unfortunately, a mechanistic study based upon an examination of the polymer's microstructure was not reported by these individuals. The present work compares the stereoregularity and molecular weight distributions via ^1H nmr and GPC analyses of the poly(methyl methacrylates) prepared with both a Ziegler-Natta catalyst $\text{Co}(\text{acac})_3$ - ZnEt_2 and with benzoyl peroxide.

The ^1H nmr analyses of the poly(methyl methacrylates) are based, in part, upon the approach used by Borey and Tiers¹. The isotactic (I), syndiotactic (S), and atactic (H) percentages were derived from the intensities of the respective peaks. The percentage of tacticities of the poly(methyl methacrylates) are given in Table 1. The percentages of different fractions of poly(methyl

TABLE 1—NMR (ANALYSIS DATA OF TACTICITIES OF POLY-METHYL METHACRYLATES)

Expt. no.*	Catalyst	Content of different units		
		Isotactic I%	Syndiotactic S%	Atactic H%
1	$\text{Co}(\text{acac})_3$ - ZnEt_2 (Zn/Co=2)	4.0	61.0	35.0
2	$\text{Co}(\text{acac})_3$ - ZnEt_2 (Zn/Co=3)	5.0	59.4	35.6
3	Benzoyl peroxide	4.4	61.9	33.5

* (1) $[\text{MMA}] = 2.5 \text{ M}$, $[\text{Co}(\text{acac})_3] = 0.025 \text{ M}$, $[\text{ZnEt}_2] = 0.05 \text{ M}$; (2) $[\text{MMA}] = 2.5 \text{ M}$, $[\text{Co}(\text{acac})_3] = 0.025 \text{ M}$, $[\text{ZnEt}_2] = 0.075 \text{ M}$; (3) $[\text{MMA}] = 2.5 \text{ M}$, $[\text{Peroxide}] = 0.025 \text{ M}$.

methacrylate) obtained from the $\text{Co}(\text{acac})_3$ - ZnEt_2 catalyst system at different Zn/Co ratios compare well with the literature reports of poly(methyl methacrylates) obtained by well-known free radical initiators^{1,5} and Ziegler-Natta type catalyst which are known to have radical properties². Moreover, the tacticity analysis compares well with that obtained from the poly(methyl methacrylate) prepared in this laboratory with benzoyl peroxide under conditions similar to that used in the present catalyst system, namely, $\text{Co}(\text{acac})_3$ - ZnEt_2 .

The GPC analysis of polymers prepared in experiments (1) and (3) gave the \bar{M}_w/\bar{M}_n values of 28.7 and 24.6 respectively. Generally, soluble Ziegler-Natta type catalysts have been found to give narrow molecular weight ratios⁶. The \bar{M}_w/\bar{M}_n values for soluble catalyst are in the region of 2 to 4 and those for heterogeneous catalysts are generally much higher. Despite the fact that the catalyst system $\text{Co}(\text{acac})_3$ - ZnEt_2 is soluble in benzene, the \bar{M}_w/\bar{M}_n values are much higher than those expected from a soluble Ziegler type catalyst. However, the \bar{M}_w/\bar{M}_n values of polymer from this catalyst were found to be in the range found for poly(methyl methacrylate) obtained from the radical catalyst benzoyl peroxide (expt. 3). These results suggest that the catalyst system $\text{Co}(\text{acac})_3$ - ZnEt_2 has radical characteristics in the polymerization of methyl methacrylate under

the conditions investigated. This is the first example with reasonable supporting data for a radical process using $\text{Co}(\text{acac})_3$ - ZnEt_2 in the polymerization of methyl methacrylate. Additional studies are in progress.

Experimental

Methyl methacrylate (Koch-Light) was freed from inhibitors and distilled under reduced pressure (N_2 -atmosphere). Cobalt(III) acetylacetonate and ZnEt_2 were prepared according to standard procedures⁷. Dry, reagent grade benzene was stored over sodium wire.

Polymerization was carried out in a dry box which was continually flushed with dry N_2 . Benzene, $\text{Co}(\text{acac})_3$, methyl methacrylate and ZnEt_2 were taken in that order in a specially designed flask inside the dry box. The flask was lightly stoppered and thermostated ($40 \pm 0.1^\circ$) for 3 h. The mixture was then poured into acidified ethanol. The polymer was filtered and dried. Prior to nmr analysis, the polymers were reprecipitated three times with acetone-ethanol.

The ^1H nmr analyses were performed on a Varian XL-300 spectrometer (sample from expts. 1 and 3) and a Bruker spectrometer (sample from expt. 2) at room temperature in CDCl_3 . Proton chemical shifts are in ppm from TMS in CDCl_3 . GPC analyses were performed with a Waters unit which was calibrated with styrene standards. The column used had the following parameters: support: Ultrastaygel E linear; mobile phase: THF; sample: THF; column temperature: 30° ; detection: refractive index; run-rate: 1.0 ml min^{-1} .

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